

**Exploring the therapeutic potential of a photography intervention during
COVID-19: Doctoral College Conference 2022 Abstract**

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Evidence points to increased levels of psychological distress resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic. There is a need for self-administered, low cost, and accessible interventions that facilitate wellbeing and growth. This study used a randomised controlled trial (RCT) design to investigate the effects of a two-week positivity and hope-oriented photography intervention on wellbeing and posttraumatic growth in comparison to a control group who did not receive the intervention. Participants were adults between the ages of 21 and 80 living in the UK recruited between May and August 2020, during the first UK national lockdown ($n=109$). Data were collected at baseline, immediately post-intervention, and at one-month follow-up. After adjusting for baseline wellbeing, both wellbeing and PTG were significantly higher in the intervention group compared to the control group following intervention completion, with this effect remaining similar at one-month follow-up. These findings offer preliminary evidence that photography could hold therapeutic value for some people living through the pandemic. Additionally, semi-structured interviews were conducted with a subsection of participants ($n=10$) exploring the content and meaning of their photographs, which highlighted new perspectives held about the physical environment, the importance of connection with others, and valuable lessons learned about themselves. Limitations include high drop-out rates at follow-up, not exploring mediators of change, and the sample being unrepresentative of the wider UK population. Implications for supporting posttraumatic growth and wellbeing during and beyond the pandemic through self-administered interventions will be discussed.